

Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to estimate the effect of chief executive officer on the firm value of non-financial services companies trading on the Nigeria Exchange Group from 2017 to 2021. 375 observations were used and multiple linear regression technique was used to analyse the data. According to the findings, ownership power, expert power, and prestige power all contribute positively to firm valuation. The reason is that chief executive officer share ownership promotes better decision making, which in turn increases the value of the firm. The quality of the chief executive officer decisions tends to improve with the length of their tenure in the position, which is indicative of their professionalism and expertise.

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1. Introduction

The primary goal of a firm is to achieve a maximum profit and thus to improve the welfare of its owners or shareholders (Rochmah & Ardianto, 2020). Shareholder welfare can be improved through firm value (Setiawan et al., 2016; Tahu & Susilo, 2017). Firm value is defined as the firm's market price value because it can provide investors or shareholders prosperity if the share price increases (Triani & Tarmidi, 2019). If the firm has a high value, investors will be attracted to invest in the firm (Setyawan & Devie, 2017). Furthermore, Endri and Fathony (2020) believe that firm value results from the firm's performance in one period. The better the firm's performance, the more likely potential investors will invest. In other words, the firm value will shape investors' perceptions of the firm's success rate, which is reflected in the share price.

Firm value is also part of the achievement of relatively consistent firm performance. This consistent performance achievement is the work of the entire board of directors or management in the firm. In this context, a chief executive officer (CEO) as the main director has a dominant role in a firm decision making process. Thus, CEO performance can contribute to the improvement of firm value (Setyawan & Devie, 2017).

CEO in Nigeria is an executive officer who has the highest position in a firm. CEO is fully responsible on the firm performance. The CEO may intervene the firm business as the CEO decision has implication on the

firm's strategy and policies (Kassim et al., 2013; Saidu, 2019; Wei, 2019). Sheikh (2018) found evidence that there is a strong relationship between CEO and firm performance. For instance, the role of Steve Jobs as CEO of Apple Inc. was to make the firm to be the international leader in technology industry. Apple Inc. became known to the public because it has good corporate values. Apple Inc. also succeeded in becoming a pioneer in technological developments in the world.

Apart from Apple Inc, a problem recently occurred with the CEO of a large airline firm in Nigeria. The chief executive officer was convicted for smuggling big Harley motorbikes and Brompton bikes. The airline was in a negative spotlight, which also impacts the firm's value. The airline's shares have begun to enter the red zone at the beginning of 2020. The share price moved from \$498 at the end of the year to a low of \$496 per share. Besides, the international rank of the company has declined. The Skytrax dropped the firm to second place for the World Best Cabin category. This might confirm that not all CEOs is able to increase firm value; some make firm values worse because of their actions. The CEO's actions can have a lot to do with the firm's value. So, the CEO is expected to have an excellent reputation for reflecting good values for the firm. The CEO is responsible for setting firm goals, making strategies, monitoring, and making decisions that impact the firm's running (Daft, 2008).

A CEO also has the authority to inspire those around him to achieve the vision and missions (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). According to the upper echelons theory, the CEO's strategy describes the cognitive values of a CEO because the CEO has a vital role in making decisions that are considered effective. The theory also proves that CEO characteristics have a relationship with firm performance. The CEO's role in the firm is significant, one of which is to make decisions that the firm will execute. With the right decisions, the firm can operate well. A CEO must know what strategies should be used so that the firm can achieve the vision that has been previously set, both short and long term visions. A vision is a series of goals of a firm that want to be realized in the future (Wibisono, 2006).

One of the most important visions in the firm is to support the firm. Certo et al. (2007) argue that the CEO has the power to impact the investment decisions of investors who have high potential. With his strengths, the CEO can have an impact on employees with the decisions that have been made. Saidu (2019) believe that groups that have companies have a hypothesis that, when managers lead a firm, there is a tendency that managers will work to achieve the targets set by the firm. According to Lasswell et al. (2017), power is a relationship between people or groups that can influence the actions of other people or groups according to the wishes of the first party. The power or power possessed by the CEO can come from reputation (prestige power), shares he owns (power held), experience (tenure), formal position (structural power) and other non-financial information that investors also consider to assess the firm's future prospects. Chief executive officer can be defined as the power of the CEO in overcoming obstacles to achieve the desired results (Wei, 2019).

Apart from the strength of the CEO, the CEO can also take advantage of several factors, such as experience, expertise, skills, and knowledge in making decisions for the firm (Hillman & Dalziel, 2003). The experience here can be seen from a CEO in a firm. CEOs who have greater powers can increase expertise related to the corporate sector so that companies can compete in their fields (Li & Patel, 2019). Li et al. (2016) also agree with this; the CEO who has led the firm for a long time has broader knowledge in his work environment. Besides that, CEOs who have experience from various companies and different industries can also make decisions that benefit the firm (Li & Patel, 2019).

Certo (2003) also argues that the board of directors describes non-financial information. Such as experience, abilities and social connections. That is important for investors to make the right investment decisions. This study will use data from non-financial companies for the 2014-2018 period listed on the Nigeria Share Exchange. Researchers used the 2014-2018 period because, in that year, there was something provided by the Nigerian government for foreign investors who wanted to invest. This was fulfilled with investor investment during 2014-2018 based on data from the Nigerian Investment Coordinating Board (BKPM RI)². The information generated from this period is the latest information which is expected to present this research in accordance with the current state of the firm with data from the latest reports.

Dowell et al. (2011) showed that CEO strength has a positive relationship with firm value. Sheikh (2018) also shows that the greater the power the CEO has, the greater the value of the firm he leads. Han, Nanda, and Silveri (2016) examined the effect of Chief executive officer on firm performance. The results show that Chief executive officer shows a positive relationship with firm performance. This is because the CEO has the power to reduce conflict and solve problems so that he can make decisions more quickly and effectively. Wu et al. (2011) state that taking decisions that are concentrated by the CEO will result in high performance, thus showing good performance variability in the firm. In contrast, Bebchuk et al. (2011) stated that Chief executive officer has a negative relationship with firm value. Research conducted by Wei (2019) states that Chief executive officer has a positive and negative relationship to firm performance.

The existence of inconsistencies in research results, and in Nigeria itself, creates a research gap in this study, so it will be interesting to examine the relationship between Chief executive officer and firm value in Nigeria. The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between the power of the firm's president director as measured by ownership power, expert power and prestige power with firm value. This study uses a quantitative approach. The independent variable of this study is the power of the CEO (Chief executive officer) and the dependent variable is the value of the firm.

This study uses secondary data sources from the annual reports of non-financial companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2017-2021, with a total sample of 375 research samples. This study contributes in providing information regarding the relationship between Chief executive officer and firm value as well as consideration for investors to invest in companies that can generate maximum returns from the management side, namely Chief executive officer consisting of ownership power, tenure power, prestige power and firm value because in the results of this study are the strength of the CEO has a positive relationship with firm value.

The paper structures are as follows: Section 2 describes the theoretical basis and hypothesis development, Section 3 describes the research approach, data sources, sample selection, variables and technical analysis used, Section 4 contains the results of the analysis and discussion of research results, and in Section 5 contains the contents of the research, limitations and suggestions.

2. Literature Review

Jensen and Meckling (1976) suggest an agency relationship that becomes a contract between the owner of the capital as principal and the director as the agent. The contract in question is a detailed explanation of what the director must do to manage the funds that investors have provided as well as a balanced distribution of returns so that the contract can be assessed as good. The director here has an obligation to be accountable for what investors have entrusted to him (Arifin, 2005). Agency theory illustrates that strong CEOs use their strengths to fulfil desired goals which in most cases are inconsistent with shareholders (Tien et al., 2013). Based on this theory, experts suggest that a firm can manage its assets so that it can minimize unnecessary expenses and maximize profits. If the firm pays attention to the interests of shareholders so that the firm can provide maximum profit as expected by stakeholders.

Upper echelons theory is a theory developed by Hambrick and Mason (1984) which states that organizational outcomes such as strategic choices can be predicted from a managerial background. This means that this theory can predict the future of an organization through its manager organization. This theory also views that top managers can produce organizational results. The results of a good and effective strategy can be seen as a reflection of the values and cognitive bases that have a relationship with the organization (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Top managers are the main decision-makers in an organization, so the decisions taken have a large and direct impact on the organization. As decision-makers, top managers have responsibility for the organization's organization.

Overall, executives' roles and characteristics will be particularly related to organizational outcomes because they have responsibility for the organization (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). This theory suggests that the organization deals with top executives. Their experiences, values, and personalities have an impact, especially in dealing with situations that will relate to the choices or decisions they will choose. The theory also holds that the executives (top executives) greatly determine their choice of strategy (strategic choice), which ultimately determines its performance.

In some companies, there is a main director (CEO) who owns shares in the firm he leads. The shares he owns are a form of power that is often referred to as ownership power (Han, Nanda, & Silveri, 2016). The greater the share ownership of a firm led by the CEO, the greater the Chief executive officer (Han et al., 2016). The many challenges faced indicate that only CEOs who have the power can easily turn strategy into action, manage processes efficiently, and increase profits to create long-term companies and increase firm value (Ulrich, 1998). Ownership power is a formal form of power that can directly impact the CEO's decision-making process. In this case, the strength of the CEO can be shown by how much impact the decisions he makes for the organization.

If the CEO owns shares in the firm, then the interests of the CEO will be the same as other owners of capital. The greater the number of shares the CEO has in the firm, the more power the CEO has in the firm he leads. So that in this case, the CEO will try to make decisions that can increase firm value and increase the wealth of shareholders, including himself. Based on the description above, the hypothesis in this study can be proposed as follows.

H₁: CEO share ownership is positively related to firm value

Expert power is the CEO's power, which is based on knowledge and experience in relevant fields and in accordance with the firm to gain access related to firm information. This knowledge and experience is the

source of strength for the CEO to gain trust so that he has the confidence to get advice from the CEO (Sudana & Aristina, 2017). CEOs who have more experience can assist companies in obtaining and providing information. Han et al. (2016) stated that the longer the CEO's tenure, the more knowledge the CEO has. The longer the CEO has been able to signal that they have a high level of professionalism and expertise that can influence the decisions he makes. CEOs who have experience are better able to increase firm value because they can make more effective decisions. The CEO's own experience can be seen from his presence in a firm. The longer the new CEO, the greater the experience he has, the greater his power to make decisions that can increase firm value. Based on the description above, the hypothesis in this study can be stated as follows.

H₂: CEO tenure is positively related to firm value

Prestige power is the CEO's strength which can be seen from the positive perceptions that the CEO has (Wu et al., 2011). A good reputation can be obtained from an educational background and relationships with external parties such as the government, politics and other influential people. The CEO has a connection that allows them to gain access to information that is beneficial in decision making for the firm (Pennings, 1980).

CEOs who have a good educational background are qualified in managing companies (D'Aveni & Kesner, 1993). By having a good reputation, the CEO will not trust employees and related outsiders. With this belief, decision-making will be easier to make. The reputation that the CEO can see from the awards he gets for being CEO. The more awards the CEO gets, the better the reputation he gets and the easier the decision-making process to increase firm value. Based on the description above, the hypothesis in this study can be stated as follows.

H₃: Prestige power is positively related to firm value

3. Methodology

This research uses quantitative data in the form of secondary data from 2017-2021. Sources of data consists of annual reports of listed non-financial services companies on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The population/sample of this study is 75. The study uses control variables to explain the phenomenon optimally because other variables can also influence the dependent variable. The control variables are firm size, leverage and profitability. The study chooses these variables because previous researches have been shown to have a significant effects on firm value (Adiputra & Hermawan, 2020; Tien et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2011). The paper uses control variables to explain the phenomenon optimally because other variables can also influence the dependent variable. The regression model for this study is as follows:

$$FV_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 OWN_{it} + \beta_2 TEN_{it} + \beta_3 PRES_{it} + \beta_4 PROF_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \beta_6 SIZE_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Whereas:

FV = Firm value is measured by Tobin's Q, which is market value divided by book value (Han et al., 2016; Sheikh, 2018)

OWN = CEO share ownership measured by percentage of CEO shares in the firm (Han et al., 2016)

TEN = CEO Tenure, measured by the number of years the CEO has served at the firm (Han et al., 2016; Sheikh, 2018)

PRES = Prestige power, measured by dummy variable, given a value of 1 if the CEO received an award during his tenure; otherwise, it will be given a value of 0 (Wu et al., 2011).

PROF = Profitability, measured by net income divided by total assets (Han et al., 2016; Rochmah & Ardianto, 2020; Utami & Inanga, 2011).

LEV = Leverage, measured by total debt divided by total assets (Han et al., 2016; Rochmah & Ardianto, 2020; Utami & Inanga, 2011).

SIZE = firm size, measured by the natural logarithm of total assets (Han et al., 2016; Rochmah & Ardianto, 2020; Utami & Inanga, 2011).

α = Alpha (Constant)

β_{1-6} = Beta coefficients (slope)

i = Firm script

t = Year script

ε = Error term

4. Results and Discussion

The firm value, which is proxied by using Tobin's Q, shows that the firm value in this study has an average of 0.93, a standard deviation of 0.86, which indicates that the data are well spread. The highest firm value is 4.81, and the lowest firm value is 0.01. Chief executive officer in this study is proxied by three measurements, namely ownership power, expert power and prestige power. Ownership power which is proxied by ownership, has an average of 0.04, a standard deviation of 0.10. The highest value is 0.95, and the lowest value is 0.00, which indicates that there are still CEOs who do not have power through share ownership in the firm where they work. Expert power, which is proxied by tenure, has an average of 12.61, which explains that the average length of time as a CEO in the study sample is 12 years and a standard deviation of 10.69. The maximum value is 48, and the minimum value is 1. Prestige power is proxied by the interlock, which is measured by a dummy; if the CEO gets an award during his tenure will be given a value of 1 and, if not given 0. The total observations is 375 with a frequency value of 1 of 131 with a percentage of 40.7% and a frequency of 0 values of 191 with a percentage of 59.3%; this shows that CEOs who received awards during their tenure were fewer than those who did not receive awards during their tenure.

Table 1. Descriptive test results

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tobin's Q	375	0.01900	4.81318	0.9374953	0.86459621
Ownership	375	0.00001	0.95570	0.0472796	0.10335933
Tenure	375	1	48	12.61	10.679
Prestige	375	0	1	0.41	0.492
Firm Size	375	24.72953	33.47373	28.7594546	1.60888888
LEV	375	0.03873	0.98948	0.4993035	0.20528745
PROF	375	-0.39184	0.24558	0.0279020	0.07853341

Profitability has a standard deviation of 0.07 with an average of 0.02, a maximum value of 0.24, and a minimum value of -0.39. The standard deviation of leverage is 0.20, with an average of 0.49. The highest leverage is 0.98, and the lowest is 0.03. The firm's size has a mean of 28.75 and a standard deviation of 1.60. In this study, the largest firm size was 33.47, while the smallest value was 24.72.

Table 2. Pearson correlation test results

	Tobin's Q	Tenure	Ownership	Prestige	Size	Lev	PROF
Tobin's Q	1.0000						
Tenure	0.3390*** (0.0000)	1.0000					
Ownership	0.1259** (0.0239)	0.1392** (0.0124)	1.0000				
Prestige	0.3463*** (0.0000)	0.3542*** (0.0000)	0.0518 (0.3544)	1.0000			
Size	-0.0332 (0.5524)	-0.1853*** (0.0008)	-0.1927*** (0.0005)	0.1165** (0.0367)	1.0000		
Lev	-0.2272*** (0.0000)	-0.0722 (0.1960)	-0.0717** (0.0412)	-0.1138** (0.0412)	0.3144*** (0.0000)	1.0000	
PROF	0.3752*** (0.0000)	0.1526*** (0.0061)	-0.1175** (0.0351)	0.1996*** (0.0003)	0.0654 (0.2419)	-0.3058*** (0.0000)	1.0000

p-value in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

The Pearson correlation test is a test to measure the relationship between two random variables (Booth & Zhou, 2017). From the results of the Pearson test, it can be seen that expert power (tenure) and prestige power (prestige) have a positive relationship with firm value (Tobin's Q) at a significance level of 1%, while for ownership power (ownership) and firm value (Tobin's Q) there is a positive relationship at the 5% significance level.

This test is carried out to assess whether or not there is a functional relationship between the dependent and independent variables. As shown in Table 2 shows the results of the regression model. From this table, it can be seen that ownership power and firm value indicate a relationship. This is evidenced by the p-value of 0.004, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.01. Thus, the H_1 can be accepted.

Table 2 also shows the relationship between expert power and firm value is existed as a positive relationship between expectancy power (tenure) and firm value at a significance of 1% is approved. Thus, H_1 is accepted, and H_0 is rejected. Moreover, a relationship between prestige power and firm value is also found in this study. The Table 2 shows that prestige power also has a positive relationship with firm value at a significance of 1%. For the control variable, PROF has a positive relationship with firm value for the regression model above at a significance level of 1%, while for the control variable leverage has a negative relationship with firm value for the above regression model at a significance level of 5% for ownership power, 1% for expert power and 10% for prestige power. The control variable firm size has no relationship with the firm value for the regression model above.

Table 3. Multiple linear regression analysis

Variable	Firm Value		
Ownership	1.298*** (0.004)		
Tenure		0.0246*** (0.000)	
Prestige			0.515*** (0.000)
PROF	3.297*** (0.000)	2.476*** (0.000)	2.579*** (0.000)
Lev	-0.548** (0.026)	-0.650*** (0.006)	-0.450* (0.060)
Firmsize	0.00968 (0.749)	0.0306 (0.298)	-0.0264 (0.365)
Constant	0.779 (0.354)	0.00280 (0.997)	1.640** (0.041)
Observations	375	375	375
R-squared	0.145	0.209	0.203

p-value in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Based on the research results, it is known that ownership power has a positive and significant positive relationship with firm value. This can be interpreted that the greater the ownership power of the president director or CEO in the firm, the firm value will also increase. This is evidenced by the ownership power value of 0.004 with a significance level of 0.01. Ownership power referred to here is the shares owned by the CEO in the firm he holds. In stewardship theory, a high commitment to the firm will make the CEO act as a steward (servant) to serve the interests of the firm and create wealth and maximize the firm's future opportunities for shareholders (Tien et al., 2013).

The share ownership he owns will make him have the same goal as the shareholders, namely the firm's profit. The CEO will make decisions that are considered effective and efficient in order to create better corporate value so that the firm can continue to run. The greater the share ownership the CEO has, the better the CEO will make decisions to increase firm value so that shareholders will be more prosperous. This can be a positive signal to investors that the CEO can lead the firm in a good direction. With this, the CEO has the ability to convince investors to invest in the firm. A high share value also reflects that the firm has a high corporate value. This research is also in line with research conducted by Dowell et al. (2011) and Sheikh (2018), which states that Chief executive officer has an influence on firm value. However, this result is not in line with the research of Chiu, Chen, Cheng, and Hung (2019), which explains that the positive results are not significant, where although strong CEOs tend to cause higher agency costs, they can create more benefits for the firm by increasing organizational efficiency and resource utilization.

Expert Power has a positive and significant relationship to firm value so that H₁ is accepted. Expert Power is the CEO's strength that we can see from the experience and knowledge the CEO has. CEOs who have more experience are considered to be able to assist companies in obtaining and providing information. The longer the CEO's position can be a signal that the level of professionalism and expertise of the CEO is getting greater and can increase his power in influencing the decisions he makes. CEOs who have more experience are considered to be able to increase firm value. The longer the CEO is in office, the more experience he has, so the greater his power to make decisions that are considered to increase the value of the firm.

Prestige power is positively related to firm value. Prestige power is the CEO's strength that comes from the positive perceptions he has because of his reputation. This reputation can come from an educational background and relations with external parties, as well as other parties, such as the government, politicians and other related people. By having a good reputation, the CEO will be trusted by employees and related external parties. With this belief, decision-making will be easier to make. The reputation that the CEO has can be seen from the awards he gets for being CEO. The more awards the CEO gets, the better the reputation he gets so that decision-making will be easier to increase firm value.

In this study, there are several control variables used, including leverage, PROF and firm size. Based on the multiple linear regression tests that have been carried out, the results show that PROF has a significant positive relationship with firm value. Leverage is negatively related to firm value. Firm size is not related to

firm value. These results are inline with research from Li and Yu (2011), which also confirms a positive relationship between PROF and firm value and a negative relationship between leverage and firm value. Several other studies (Ibhagui & Olokoyo, 2018; Olokoyo, 2013) also found a significant relationship between leverage and firm value, where a higher level of leverage in the firm's capital structure is associated with stronger firm value. On the other hand, the results of this study are not in line with research from Qiu et al. (2016) and Hirdinis (2019), who found that firm size is positively related to firm value, which indicates that large firm size will be able to attract investors to invest so that firm value increases.

5. Conclusions

This study assesses whether there is an influence between chief executive officer and firm value. Ownership power, which is proxied by CEO share ownership, has a positive effect on firm value. This means that, in Nigeria, the CEO who owns shares in the firm he leads is able to influence the value of the firm. Expert power, which is proxied by CEO tenure, has a positive effect on firm value. This means that the longer the CEO has served in a firm, the CEO will have power because they have received information and the ability to lead a firm. This information and ability are obtained from the experience of the CEO, who had led the firm. The longer the CEO is in office, the more it will increase the firm's value. Prestige power, as measured by the CEO's dummy, has a positive effect on firm value. This means that the CEO who gets an award as long as he leads the firm will have a positive influence on the firm so that it can increase firm value. This can be explained because prestige power will make the CEO have high competence recognized by other parties so that the CEO can maximize firm value.

This study provides empirical evidence on the relationship between Chief executive officer and firm value as well as consideration for investors to invest in companies that can generate maximum returns from the management side, namely Chief executive officer consisting of ownership power, expert power, prestige power and firm value. The results of this study show Chief executive officer is proven to have a positive relationship with firm value.

The limitation of this study is that the researcher only uses three measurements to measure chief executive officer using and does not use other measurements due to the limitations of sampling in Nigeria. The proxies used also have many shortcomings and do not describe all the variables assessed for the sample period of this study using only a five-year time span, namely 2017-2021. The researcher suggests using another measure in measuring chief executive officer in order to obtain comprehensive results about the effect of chief executive officer on firm value.

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